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“Genetic Variability at the ADP Ribose Binding Site of SARS-CoV-2 Macrodomain and Predicting Its Effects on ADP Ribose Binding”

Background:

Previously we reported our analysis on the structural diversity of binding pockets found on the SARS-CoV-2 Main protease, methyltransferase, and papain-like protease. We then shifted our focus on the SARS-CoV-2 macrodomain (nsp3-Mac1).

There are six macrodomain classes based on structural similarity. Most viral macrodomains fall into the MacroD-like family, the same as human homologs MacroD1 and MacroD2, which remove mono-ADP-ribose (MAR) from macromolecules. (Xu et al., 2008)

Non-structural protein 3 (nsp3) is a large multidomain protein encoded by SARS-CoV-2 RNA. Within nsp3, there are three tandem macrodomains, including Mac1, Mac2, and Mac3. In contrast to Mac2 and Mac3, Mac1 is conserved among coronaviruses (CoVs), and it binds to mono- and poly-ADP-ribose and hydrolyzes MAR from target proteins. Mac1 is known to interfere with the immune response, possibly due to its ability to remove ADP-ribose from ADP-ribosylated proteins and RNA as part of the host's immune response's intricacies. (Alhammad et al., 2020)

PARPs (poly ADP-ribose polymerases) add MAR subunits to their substrates after being induced by interferon to inhibit viral replication. Therefore Mac1's function is opposite to PARPs since, by de-MARylating target proteins, it contributes to viral evasion from the host defense mechanism (Alhammad et al., 2020).

In a previous study, a viral agent with mutated macrodomain replicated poorly in macrophages in the bone marrow, the primary cells in the innate immune response. This finding shows that macrodomain inhibition may help reduce viral replication. (Grunewald et al., 2019)

There is further experimental evidence that supports the role of conserved macrodomain in CoV's virulence and suppression of immune response. Eriksson and her colleagues showed that mutating a conserved asparagine residue of Mac1 to an alanine attenuated the hydrolase activity of Mac1 in SARS-CoV (Eriksson et al., 2008). Additionally, Fehr and his colleagues showed that the asparagine-to-alanine substitution in the hepatotropic mouse hepatitis virus strain A59 (MHV-A59) macrodomain resulted in virus attenuation in the wild type mice. (Fehr et al., 2014) Furthermore, the asparagine-to-alanine Mac1 mutant also attenuates SARS-CoV viral load in a mouse model of severe respiratory disease. (Fehr et al., 2016).

In summary, Mac1 could be an attractive target for small-molecule antivirals with the caveat that a highly selective compound would need to be found in order to discriminate between the human and the viral macrodomains. (Alhammad et al., 2020)

In this report, I will explain how we identified the ADP ribose (ADPr) binding site of Mac1 and its druggability measure, and list the residues lining that site. Then I will present diversity dendrograms of UniProt entries of Alpha- and Betacoronavirus genera while focusing on Mac1 ADPr binding site. Following that, I will show the predicted effects on ADPr binding to Mac1 due to changes in Gibbs free energy of ligand binding as a result of the non-synonymous variants that Nicola De Maio, our collaborator from European Bioinformatics Institute, has identified at ADPr binding site.

Method:

Step 1: Assessing the druggability of SARS-CoV-2 nsp3-Mac1 ADPr binding site with SiteMap (PDB: 6w02).

Using ICM function PocketFinder (Molsoft, SD) we found the potential drug-binding sites using the nsp3-Mac1 x-ray crystal structure (PDB: 6w02). Then using SiteMap (Schrodinger, NY) we assessed the druggability of the binding sites using the druggability score (Dscore). The ADPr binding site of nsp3-Mac1 has a Dscore of 0.95 indicative of a druggable site.

Figure 1. Druggability analysis of SARS-CoV-2 nsp3-Mac1 ADPr binding site. The red pocket is occupied by ADPr.

Step 2. Determine the residues that line the ADPr binding site (PDB: 6w02).

Using ICM, we found the amino acid sidechains that face the ADPr binding pocket within its 2.8 Å vicinity. We identified twenty-nine sidechains in total which include: Asp22, Ile23, Asn37, Ala38, Ala39, Asn40, Hie45, Gly46, Gly47, Gly48, Val49, Ala50, Gly51, Ala52, Gly97, Pro12, Leu12, Leu12, Ser12, Ala12, Gly13, Ile13, Phe13, Pro13, Ala15, Val15, Phe15, Asp15, Leu16 as shown in figure 2.

Figure 2. The neighboring residues lining the ADPr binding pocket of Mac1.

Step 3. Make diversity dendrograms for sequences of the Alpha- and Betacoronavirus genera entries in UniProt database.

In the context of the emergence of future MERS-like or SARS-like coronaviruses from the bat strains circulating in bat reservoir species, it is imperative to do a broad survey of viral proteins to identify the best strategies for the development of broad-spectrum viral inhibitors. (Sheahan et al., 2020) For this exact reason, we are looking at twenty-seven reviewed sequences from Uniprot, where six belong to entries of Alphacoronavirus genus and twenty-one belong to the Betacoronavirus genus. We then assess their amino acid variability at nsp3-Mac1 ADPr binding site (PDB: 6w02).

I made a diversity dendrogram focusing on the sidechains from step2. Shown below in figure 3 is the diversity dendrogram, where the consensus profile at each of the 29 sidechains is shown. Strikingly, only 11 out of 29 sidechains are conserved across these 27 entries: N37, A39, N40, H45, G48, A50, G97, S128, G130, I131, F132.

Figure 3. The diversity dendrogram of the ADPr-binding site of Mac1 for the entries of Alpha- and Betacoronavirus genera.

Step 4: Make diversity dendrograms for reviewed sequences of the Betacoronavirus genus entries in UniProt database.

We made a diversity dendrogram of the 21 entries of the Betacoronavirus genus. As shown in figure 4, 14 out of 29 residues are conserved at Mac1 ADPr binding site: D22, N37, A39, N40, H45, G46, G48, A50, G97, L126, S128, G130, I131, F132.

Figure 4. The diversity dendrogram of Mac1 ADPr binding site residues among the UniProt entries of the Betacoronavirus genus.

Step 5: Map variations observed among Alpha- and Betacoronavirus genera entries and the variations within only the Betacoronavirus entries onto SARS-CoV-2 Mac1 crystal structure (PDB: 6w02).

We mapped the variations shown in step 3 and 4 onto SARS-CoV-2 Mac1 color-coded crystal structure such that sidechains that are variable among the entries are highlighted in orange and the conserved sidechains are shown in green. Later in step 8, the predicted effect of each variation on ligand binding is provided.

Figure 5. Mapping the genetic variation of UniProt entries belonging to Alpha- and Betacoronavirus genera (top) and among entries of Betacoronavirus genus (bottom) onto SARS-CoV-2 nsp3-Mac1 Crystal structure (PDB: 6w02). The green color shows the conserved residues and the orange color shows the non-conserved residues among the entries which were mentioned in steps 3 & 4.

Based on figure 5, it is apparent that the residues lining the adenosine part of ADPr are not conserved (orange) while the residues surrounding the terminal ribose ring are conserved (green) among the entries of Alpha- and Betacoronavirus genera.

Step 6: Assessing the genetic variability of Mac1 ADPr binding site among SARS-CoV-2 samples.

Nicola De Maio, our collaborator from Nick Goldman's lab at European Bioinformatics Institute, looked at more than 15000 SARS-CoV-2 samples and identified all mutations at the Mac1 ADPr binding site. He identified 15 non-synonymous variants as shown in table 1. For example, at residue number 23, the wild-type sidechain in SARS-CoV-2 Mac1 is isoleucine. In the sample batch Nicola has looked at, he saw that 15872 samples had isoleucine at that position while there were 2 samples with other variants at this position; one was a valine and another was a serine.

Number	Wild Type	Non-synonymous Variants
1	Ile23	I (15872), V (1)
2	Ile23	I (15872), S (1)
3	Ala39	A (15872), V (3)
4	Asn40	S (1), N (15874)
5	His45	Y (1), H (15874)
6	Gly46	*(1), G (15874)
7	Gly48	C (1), G (15873)
8	Val49	I (2), V (15871)
9	Ala52	A (15873), V (1)
10	Ala129	A (15781), V (1)
11	Ile131	I (15781), F (1)
12	Phe132	V (1), F (15781)
13	Pro136	P (15760), L (6)
14	Pro136	P (15760), S (6)
15	Leu160	L (15870), F (1)

Table 1. The non-synonymous variants at Mac1 ADPr binding site across more than 15000 SARS-CoV-2 samples. * denotes that the mutation has caused a premature stop codon at position Gly46, and the patient's status with this mutation in their viral sample was marked as "released".

Step 7. Energy calculations for the SARS-CoV-2 variants at nsp3-MAC1 ADPr binding site and predicting their effects on ADPr binding.

To predict the effect of these mutations on the binding of a known Mac1 ligand, ADPr (PDB: 6w02), we estimated the difference in the binding energy of the ligand between the wild type and the mutated forms of the protein with ICM (Molsoft, San Diego). ICM calculates the change in Gibbs binding energy (dG_{bind} in kcal/mol) of the ligand as the energy of the protein-ligand complex minus the energy of the isolated protein and ligand. The difference in binding energy (ddG_{bind}), which is what we are interested in, is dG_{bind} [mutant] minus dG_{bind} [wild-type]. Since the precision of the method is about 2 kcal/mol, ddG_{bind} values > 2 kcal/mol indicate mutations that significantly penalize ligand binding. (Schapira et al., 1999) The color-coded structure in figure 6 highlights the variants among the SARS-CoV-2 samples at ADPr-binding site of nsp3-Mac1 based on their effects on ligand binding.

Residue Number	Wild Type	Mutant	ddGbind	dGbind_wild	dGbind_mut
23	ile	val	-1.3	-67.1	-68.4
23	ile	Ser	1.2	-67.1	-65.9
39	ala	val	-0.6	-67.1	-67.6
40	asn	ser	1.8	-67.1	-65.3
45	hie	tyr	-3.3	-67.1	-70.4
48	gly	cys	5.0	-67.1	-62.1
49	val	ile	-1.6	-67.1	-68.6
52	ala	val	-2.3	-67.1	-69.4
129	ala	val	-3.2	-67.1	-70.3
131	ile	phe	4.3	-67.1	-62.8
132	phe	val	-1.4	-67.1	-68.5
136	pro	leu	-0.2	-67.1	-67.3
136	pro	ser	0.1	-67.1	-67.0
160	leu	phe	-4.0	-67.1	-71.1

Figure 6. Energy calculations of non-synonymous mutations at SARS-CoV-2 nsp3-Mac1 ADPr binding site to predict their effect on ADPr binding. The colored areas on the mesh show the non-conserved residues across more than 15000 SARS-CoV-2 samples from COVID-19 patients. The orange-colored residues correspond to variants, G48C and I131F, which are expected to destabilize ADPr-binding significantly ($ddGbind > 2.0$ kcal/mol), while the variants corresponding to the green-colored residues are expected to affect ADPr binding to macrodomain only minimally ($ddGbind < 2$ kcal/mol). The energy unit for $ddGbind$ values is Kcal/mol. The

Looking at figure 6, we see that the $ddGbind$ values for G48C, I131F are above 2.0 Kcal/mol which is considered a significant change in binding according to a previous study. (Schapira et al., 1999) The remainder of the variants are predicted to have minor effects on ligand binding (-2 kcal/mol $< ddGbind < 2$ kcal/mol).

Based on previous studies, coronaviruses with mutations in their macrodomains are highly attenuated and in vivo cause minimal disease. This is due to the role of macrodomain in reversing ADP-ribosylation which disrupts the host's immune response. (Grunewald et al., 2019)

Below, I use sticks and surface representation to model the two SARS-CoV-2 nsp3-Mac1 variants, G48C (figure 8) and I131F (figure 10), as visualization aids.

Figure 7. The ribbon diagram of SARS-CoV-2 macrodomain variant: G48C. The corresponding ddGbind value for this mutation is 5.0 Kcal/mol. The dashed line represents the hydrogen bond between G48 and hydroxyl group on ribose sugar.

Figure 8. The surface representation of SARS-CoV-2 macrodomain variant: G48C. The corresponding ddGbind value for this mutation is 5.0 Kcal/mol.

C48 is a bulkier residue than glycine as shown in figure 8 which could be the reason for unfavorable and destabilizing predicted effect on ADPr binding with the nsp3-Mac1 at ddGbind value of 5.0 Kcal/mol. The diphosphate moiety binds to the glycine-rich segment (Gly46-Gly47-Gly48) loop on the protein which provides stabilizing effect for the proximal ribose ring in the pocket through hydrogen bonds with G46 (OH2'), G48 (OH1'). (Michalska et al., 2020)

Figure 9. The ribbon diagram of SARS-CoV-2 macrodomain variant I131F. The corresponding ddGbind value for this mutation is 4.3 Kcal/mol. The dashed line represents the hydrogen bond between I131 and oxygen atom on phosphate group on ADPr.

Figure 10. The surface representation of SARS-CoV-2 macrodomain variant: I131F. The corresponding ddGbind value for this mutation is 4.3 Kcal/mol.

Although phenylalanine is a bulkier residue than isoleucine, its bulkiness is protruded outside the pocket rather than inside the pocket where the phosphate linker is located. According to Karolina Michalska and their colleagues, the proximal ribose ring is stabilized in the pocket by hydrophobic interactions with I131. The mutation to phenylalanine may disturb this hydrophobic interaction. (Michalska et al., 2020)

In figure 11, you can view the 2D ligand-protein diagram showing the chemical interactions between ADPr and nsp3-Mac1.

Figure 11. 2D ligand-protein diagram showing the chemical interactions between ADPr and nsp3-Mac1 (PDB: 6w02). G48 and I131 are highlighted to show their hydrogen bonds with ADPr molecule. This diagram was made using PoseView in Proteins.Plus.

Step 8: Predicting the effect of all possible mutations at nsp3-Mac1 ADPr-binding site on ADPr binding.

We created an energy matrix where we consider the effect of every possible mutation on the binding of ADPr with nsp3-Mac1. Table 2 includes a list of 29 residues lining the pockets.

It is likely that the residues of the rows with green color are not making optimal interactions with ADPr. This is reflected in the very slight and non-significant lowering in ddGbind values of these residues (mutations are stabilizing) and hence the green color. On the other hand, the sidechains whose mutations are shown in orange are likely the positions where macrodomain would better interact with ADPr. As a result, the mutations of those sidechains are predicted to penalize its binding significantly and hence the orange color.

Residue Number	WT	Mutant Residue																			
		gly	ala	val	leu	ile	pro	cys	met	ser	thr	phe	tyr	trp	asn	gln	asp	glu	his	lys	arg
22	D	-0.1	-0.3	-0.1	-1.0	0.0	-1.0	-1.6	0.3	-4.2	-0.2	0.5	0.5	1.2	-1.0	0.2	0.0	0.5	-3.5	-0.4	-1.0
23	I	3.7	1.6	-1.3	-2.9	0.0	18.5	-2.5	-4.5	1.2	-0.3	0.6	1.1	-2.7	-4.3	-1.8	2.4	4.4	-2.2	-3.9	-5.9
37	N	0.6	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.2	210.3	0.3	0.0	0.1	0.2	-0.7	-4.2	-3.1	0.0	0.2	3.8	1.9	-0.6	-0.8	-4.5
38	A	4.8	0.0	5.0	2.2	9.4	-3.7	-0.1	4.6	-0.2	3.9	-4.3	-0.5	-4.7	1.5	0.9	13.4	15.9	-3.7	2.4	14.9
39	A	-0.2	0.0	-0.6	-0.5	-0.6	71.9	0.0	-0.4	0.3	-0.3	0.0	0.1	-0.6	-0.1	0.0	1.9	1.7	-0.1	-1.4	-0.8
40	N	1.8	2.4	8.7	3.7	8.5	85.8	1.1	0.7	1.8	3.9	-2.3	-2.2	4.2	0.0	0.1	2.1	4.2	-2.1	-1.4	-1.5
45	H	-0.6	-0.5	-0.5	-0.3	-0.4	-0.5	-0.3	-0.1	-0.3	-0.5	-3.0	-3.3	0.0	0.1	0.0	1.8	0.9	0.0	-1.0	-0.9
46	G	0.0	-5.3	-6.6	-6.7	-5.1	73.2	-5.9	3.2	3.7	-4.6	-3.7	-1.9	-8.2	-11.1	-7.2	-3.6	-4.8	-7.8	-6.4	-7.7
47	G	0.0	-3.1	-3.0	-3.1	-3.1	0.2	-3.1	-3.1	-3.0	-3.1	-3.0	-3.0	-3.0	-3.1	-3.3	-2.3	-2.6	-3.0	-3.2	-3.7
48	G	0.0	4.7	25.7	50.6	147.0	142.6	5.0	64.0	8.1	21.9	10.9	11.6	9.1	1.0	26.2	27.1	60.9	6.8	24.3	32.8
49	V	3.1	1.3	0.0	0.3	-1.6	21.1	2.6	0.4	2.9	3.5	46.7	21.1	18.5	-2.6	-3.6	13.5	5.5	5.7	-2.6	-10.2
50	A	0.0	0.0	-3.7	5.3	11.3	4.2	1.6	57.5	-3.1	0.2	0.5	7.8	-1.5	83.4	2.9	3.6	9.4	-1.1	5.9	5.6
51	G	0.0	0.0	0.1	-0.1	0.1	-0.5	0.0	0.0	-0.3	0.3	-4.3	-0.6	-0.3	0.1	-0.2	0.7	0.1	-0.7	-0.5	-0.7
52	A	-3.9	0.0	-2.3	7.0	5.6	-0.5	2.6	9.9	-2.6	-2.5	-0.3	-0.4	-2.8	-0.6	15.1	-0.4	1.5	-3.2	2.9	0.0
97	G	0.0	-0.6	-0.4	-0.5	-0.5	-4.3	-1.0	-4.9	0.3	-0.4	-0.4	-0.2	-0.2	-1.4	-0.5	7.1	7.0	-3.8	-4.0	-4.2
125	P	-1.8	-0.2	0.3	-7.1	-0.4	0.0	-1.8	-6.1	-0.5	0.8	-4.1	-7.2	133.5	-1.6	-14.8	6.0	6.8	-3.9	-2.7	-15.2
126	L	-0.2	0.3	0.0	0.0	-0.3	3.0	0.0	-0.5	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.3	0.7	-0.7	0.9	0.5	-3.2	-1.2	-1.3
127	L	-1.4	-0.9	-0.3	0.0	-0.4	-0.7	-0.8	-0.6	-1.0	-0.1	0.3	0.3	0.4	0.3	-0.2	3.6	2.4	-0.3	-2.1	-1.3
128	S	1.1	0.6	0.5	-0.1	0.4	49.9	0.7	0.2	0.0	1.0	0.8	0.8	1.5	2.3	-0.2	4.6	2.5	0.4	-1.1	-1.2
129	A	-2.9	0.0	-3.2	-0.5	-0.9	-0.8	0.1	-4.3	-3.4	-3.1	-0.2	-3.2	-0.2	-3.2	-4.0	4.0	0.4	-0.3	-2.1	-1.1
130	G	0.0	1.8	33.7	110.2	90.4	190.3	12.8	94.6	14.2	9.8	72.1	72.7	72.7	28.4	61.9	21.2	31.1	71.5	72.3	74.7
131	I	5.2	3.4	-0.5	1.8	0.0	16.1	2.5	8.3	8.4	4.6	4.3	4.3	0.0	-2.5	-0.9	6.0	4.1	-1.5	0.2	0.2
132	F	4.2	3.2	-1.4	-1.0	-1.5	19.8	3.3	5.4	1.1	1.7	0.0	-3.3	0.6	2.1	0.9	7.0	3.9	-2.8	-3.0	-0.8
136	P	0.0	0.0	-0.5	-0.2	-1.1	0.0	-0.1	-1.2	0.1	-0.4	2.7	3.3	19.6	-4.6	-1.3	-1.6	-1.2	-1.1	2.0	-5.0
154	A	-3.2	0.0	0.1	0.0	0.8	1.2	-3.2	-0.2	0.1	-0.2	0.1	0.0	-3.2	-3.4	-3.2	1.6	1.8	-3.6	-3.6	-1.6
155	V	0.3	0.3	0.0	-0.9	0.0	77.3	0.5	-3.0	0.5	0.1	-3.1	0.0	0.6	1.3	-2.6	7.1	2.5	-1.9	-0.2	-0.5
156	F	-1.3	-3.2	4.4	-0.9	16.8	3.2	-2.7	2.8	-2.7	2.8	0.0	-0.8	-2.5	-3.0	1.1	-2.0	-1.1	-3.1	-4.0	-3.0
157	D	-3.6	-3.3	-3.4	-3.3	-3.1	-5.2	-3.3	-3.0	-3.3	-2.8	-3.0	-3.2	-2.8	-3.1	-2.6	0.0	0.2	-3.2	-3.8	-3.5
160	L	-3.6	-3.8	-3.3	0.0	-3.2	-3.8	-2.5	-3.3	-2.7	-3.2	-4.0	-4.2	-3.7	-2.9	-3.1	-1.4	-2.5	-3.4	1.6	-3.6

Table 2. The energy matrix showing the effect of all possible mutations at SARS-COV-2 nsp3-Mac1 ADPr binding site and the predicted effect on ADPr binding. The energy unit is kcal/mol. WT = wild type residue.

Color-coding based on ddGbind value (X) in Kcal/mol
X >10.0
4.0> X >10.0
2.0> X > 4.0
-2.0> X > 2.0
-4.0> X > -2.0
-10.0> X > -4.
-10.0> X

Most of the hydrogen bonds in ADPr binding pocket make use of main chain atoms and only a few hydrogen bonds involve protein side chains. Since main sidechain interactions can be achieved using several combinations of sidechains, there is less pressure on amino acid preservation. (Michalska et al., 2020)

In the absence of a catalytic residue at ADPr-binding site, Jankevicius et al. proposed substrate-assisted catalysis. Through this enzymatic mechanism, a water molecule is responsible for nucleophilic attack on the ribose anomeric carbon atom which is activated by the Pa group. (Jankevicius et al., 2013) Based on the current macrodomain/ADPr structure (PDB: 6w02), the candidate water (Wat) molecule binds to the amide group of A50, also the carbonyl of A38, and oxygen atom of Pa and OH1' group of the proximal ribose ring of ADPr which is shown in figure 12. (Michalska et al., 2020)

Figure 12. ADPr binding site in nsp3-Mac1 (PDB:6w02). Michalska et al., 2020.

Based on the diversity dendrograms in figure 3 and 4, it is evident that A50 is preserved among the entries of Alpha- and Betacoronavirus entries while A38 is not. On the other hand, both A38 and A50 are conserved in the SARS-CoV-2 samples from the samples of COVID-19 patients Nicola De Maio has looked at.

From table 2, we see that many cells of the rows belonging to A38 and A50 are highlighted in orange which further points at the importance of these two amino acids in substrate-assisted catalysis proposed by Jankevicius et al. (Jankevicius et al., 2013).

Conclusion

We see a lot of structural diversity at the ADP-ribose binding site of the first macrodomain of SARS-CoV-2 nsp3, both across diverse coronaviruses, and across diverse SARS-CoV-2 samples. However, most of

these variations are predicted to have little impact on ADPr binding. While this structural diversity is not favourable for the design of broad-spectrum ligands, competitive inhibitors mimicking interactions made by ADPr may have a broad spectrum of action.

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